

ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE DYNAMICS OF ACINETOBACTER SPP. IN ICU

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Abstract. *Objective: to analyze the dynamics of antibiotic resistance of Acinetobacter spp. isolated from patients in ICU. To identify effective antibiotics against isolated strains.*

Material and methods. We analyzed the isolated strains and analyzed the results of determining the sensitivity of Acinetobacter spp. to antibacterial drugs. The pathogens were isolated from ICU patients in 2008-2019. Clinical material for microbiologic examination included wound secretions, bronchoalveolar lavage, abdominal cavity exudate, abscess contents, bile, urine, and blood. Microbiological studies were carried out in the laboratories of microbiological of the State Institution "RSSPMC for surgery named after V.Vakhidov"

Results. Due to the introduction of recommended protocols for antibacterial prophylaxis and treatment, methods of monitoring the effectiveness of antimicrobial therapy, the introduction of forecasting methods (identification of risk groups and more targeted antibiotic prophylaxis of nosocomial infections), effective criteria for ventilator modes, approaches to pathogenetic therapy, nutritional support, etc. since 2012, there is a decrease in the frequency of purulent-septic complications, so that in 2012-2019 in the cardiac block, it was from 1.5-1.3 to 0.3-0.1%, in the abdominal block - from 1.0-1.9 to 0.5-0.2%, in the thoracic block - from 0.7-0.5 to 0.03-0.02%.

Conclusion. The increasing antibiotic resistance of Acinetobacter spp. causes the necessity to study antibiotic grams of all strains isolated from patients for adequate choice of means of effective antibiotic therapy. The obtained data were used to optimize empirical antibiotic therapy in patients with purulent-septic complications in ICU.

Keywords: *antimicrobial therapy, Acinetobacter spp., agents of suppurative and septic complications, resistance, nosocomial infections, intensive care unit.*

INTRODUCTION

The development of infectious complications in patients with a high risk of sepsis in ICU (severe acute pancreatitis, bleeding, acute respiratory distress syndrome, PON) is the leading cause of mortality. Knowledge of the etiologic structure and antibiotic resistance of the main pathogens is essential for timely adequate antibiotic prophylaxis and empirical antibiotic therapy.

The main problematic pathogens of nosocomial infections in terms of antibiotic resistance are MRSA, MRSE, *Ps. aeruginosa*, *Kl.pneumoniae*, *E. coli*, *Acinetobacter spp.* etc. The most relevant causative agents of all hospital-acquired infections (except angiogenic infections) and sepsis are microorganisms of the Enterobacteriaceae family and non-fermenting bacteria, which include *Ps. aeruginosa* and *Acinetobacter spp.* (Wong D, 2017). *Acinetobacter* strains prior to 1970 very rarely caused infections in humans, infections were successfully treated with ampicillin, gentamicin, and carbenicillin; in 1975, reports of resistant strains appear; in 1990, *Acinetobacter* strains resistant to all ABs except carbapenems were isolated in Germany. In Hong Kong, the most frequent pathogens were *Acinetobacter johnsonii* and *Acinetobacter lwoffii*. In most countries of

the world, including Russia, *Acinetobacter baumannii* is becoming the main causative agent. Until 2004, *Acinetobacter* spp. - was the second most frequent causative agent of nosocomial infections in ICU among NSAIDs in Europe, from 2006 to 2007 it was the first most frequent pathogen in 7 leading ICUs among NSAIDs (Salzer H.J., 2009).

The following risk factors for carbapenem-resistant *Acinetobacter* infection have been described so far: large size of the hospital (more than 500 beds), prolonged hospitalization in ICU, immunosuppression, ventilator, catheterization, recent surgical intervention, aggravated antibiotic history (recent use of ceftazidime, meropenem, imipenem).

MATERIAL AND METHODS.

We analyzed the isolated strains and analyzed the results of determining the sensitivity of *Acinetobacter* spp. to antibacterial drugs. The pathogens were isolated from ICU patients in 2008-2019. Clinical material for microbiologic examination included wound secretions, bronchoalveolar lavage, abdominal cavity exudate, abscess contents, bile, urine, and blood. Identification of isolated microorganisms was performed using test kits of "Hi-Media" company, India, Interpretation of results was performed according to NCCLS/CLSI guidelines. Determination of antibiotic sensitivity of strains was performed by disk-diffusion method on Mueller-Hinton medium in accordance with CLSI (formerly NCCLS) standards.

RESULTS.

A total of 486 cultures were isolated, of which *Acinetobacter* spp. - 131 (27%). *Acinetobacter* spp. strains were isolated mainly from trachea (patients on PIVL) - 77%, drainage secretions - 15%, from blood - 8%. High level of resistance of *Acinetobacter* spp. to cephalosporins in 2008-2011 amounted to 85%, in 2012-2019 - 100%, to fluoroquinolones - 100%. - 100%, to fluoroquinolones in 2008-2011 amounted to 85%, in 2012-2019 - 100%, to aminoglycosides spp. - 100%, to aminoglycosides in 2008-2011 amounted to 85%, in 2012-2019. - 70%, in 2012-2019. - 100%, to carbapenems in 2008-2011. - 25%, in 2012-2019. - 70%.

Table 1. Results of biological field samples (%)

Biomaterial type	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Surgical wound	3,7	0,6	2,6	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Blood	10,4	11	14	5,4	3,8	2,7	-	0,6	1,2	0,4	0,2	-
From abdominal cavity	1,5	0,6	2,2	1,3	0,6	-	0,3	0,6	2,2	0,6	0,2	0,4
From pleural cavity	0,4	0,3	0,9	2	-	-	-	0,3	-	0,3	-	-
From drainage	6,3	5,3	4,8	6,7	3,7	4,3	2,4	3,8	5,6	2,6	5,3	2,1
From trachea	10	7,3	9,6	11	19	17	10	14	19	10	17	19
From bronchi	4	1	-	0,6	-	-	-	0,6	1	-	0,6	0,2
Urine	0,4	-	-	2	-	-	-	-	0,6	-	0,2	-

These data demonstrate the leading position of respiratory diseases in the structure of severe infections.

Table 2. *Acinetobacter* spp. resistance in ICU (%)

Antibiotics	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Ampicillin /sulbactam	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Amoxicillin	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Piperacillin /Tazobactam	-	-	-	82	76	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Imipenem	0	11,7	21	11,7	13	21	43	85	100	100	100	100
Meropenem	11,7	41	41	60	66,6	76	87	100	100	100	100	100
Ertapenem	-	-	-	-	-	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Cefazoline	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Cefuroxim	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Cefotaxim	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Ceftazidim	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Ceftriaxone	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Cefaperazone	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Cefaperazone /sulbactam	66,6	66,6	84	82	66,6	73	85	100	100	100	100	100
Cefepim	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Gentamicin	88	86	78	86	88	90	100	100	100	100	100	100
Amikacin	86	78	90	90	90	90	100	100	100	100	100	100
Tetracycline	66	46	17,6	17,6	26	68	66	70	100	100	100	100
Doxicycline	52	41	16	11,7	16	52	50	50	100	100	100	100
Ofloxacin	66,6	78	90	76	90	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Ciprofloxacin	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Levofloxacin	-	-	78	100	-	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Gatifloxacin	-	-	-	-	-	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Polymixin	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	5	3	4	4

Note: "-" - the study was not conducted

Fig.1. Cultivability of the most important pathogens of purulent-septic complications in ICU

Fig.2. Frequency of purulent-septic complications in ICU (%)

Analysis of microbiological monitoring data and antibiotic resistance in ICU shows that during the studied period (2008-2019), in patients undergoing PIVL, there is a tendency of prevalence of Gram-negative microflora isolation and expansion of the spectrum of isolated cultures, namely: *Klebsiella pneumonia* (17.0-29.0%), *Ps. aeruginosa* (14.0-20.5%) and *Candida* (4.2-10.0%) were dominant in 2008-2012. The drugs active against them were meropenem (60.0-30.0%S), polymyxin B (100.0-95.0%S), cefoperazone/sulbactam (72.0-58.0%), amikacin (72.0-64.0%), ofloxacin (69.0-56.0%). *St.aureus* and *Enterococcus* spp. occurred in 4.0-2.0% of cases.

Subsequent 2012-2019 among the most "topical" pathogens of hospital infections were *Acinetobacter* spp. (26.0-39.0%), *E. coli* (27.6-11.0%), *gr.r.Candida* (11.0-18.5%). The range of perorates active against them was extremely limited: polymyxin B (97.0-95.0%S), imipenem (90.0-30.0%S). Moreover, out of 50 tracheobronchial aspirate samples in 25 cases - were isolated associated. The problem was the development and progression of renal insufficiency when using amikacin in patients with PON.

RESULTS.

The effective reduction of purulent-septic complications frequency (despite the annual increase in the number of hospitalized patients) was the isolation of patients with high risk of infection with nosocomial strains, high level of SRB - 70 mg/l and more, protocols of resuscitation in case of purulent-septic complications, timely adequate antibiotic therapy. The achieved results indicate the effectiveness of the applied monitoring system, despite the high resistance of pathogens; the need for continuous control of the microbial landscape.

Due to the introduction of recommended protocols for antibacterial prophylaxis and treatment, methods of monitoring the effectiveness of antimicrobial therapy, the introduction of forecasting methods (identification of risk groups and more targeted antibiotic prophylaxis of nosocomial infections), effective criteria for ventilator modes, approaches to pathogenetic therapy, nutritional support, etc. since 2012, there is a decrease in the frequency of purulent-septic complications, so that in 2012-2019 in the cardiac block, it was from 1.5-1.3 to 0.3-0.1%, in the abdominal block - from 1.0-1.9 to 0.5-0.2%, in the thoracic block - from 0.7-0.5 to 0.03-0.02% (Fig.2).

CONCLUSION

In the structure of pathogens of nosocomial infections in ICU - *Acinetobacter* spp. is the leading one, which has high resistance to all groups of antibacterial drugs. Over the last 12 years, the increase in the isolation rate of this pathogen amounted to: 5.4 - 39%, i.e., an increase of 7 times. *Acinetobacter* is capable of causing infections of any localization. The increasing antibiotic resistance of *Acinetobacter* spp. causes the necessity to study antibiotic grams of all strains isolated from patients for adequate choice of means of effective antibiotic therapy. The obtained data were used to optimize empirical antibiotic therapy in patients with purulent-septic complications in ICU.

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